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TV Towar,Badlapur, MSief

ikfkfed Lrj ij ljdkjh , oa xj&ljdkjh fo|ky; ka dh J\$Brk ea l gk; d
dkjdka dk %dkuij e. My ds fo'k\$ l UnHkZ ea %ryukRed v/; ; u

Education

v'k\$ d\$kj
vfl LVWV i kQ\$ j

chO, MO foHkx] Mko thoihovkjomho iVsy egkfo|ky;] vjksy] dkuij uxj

I kjka k

iLrq 'k\$ v/; ; u ea 'k\$driz }jkk "ikfkfed Lrj ij ljdkjh , oa xj&ljdkjh
fo|ky; ka dh J\$Brk ea l gk; d dkjdka dk ryukRed v/; ; u fd; k x; k g\$ ftl ea dkuij
e. My ds 120 ljdkjh ikfkfed fo|ky; , oa 120 xj&ljdkjh ikfkfed fo|ky; dty 240
J\$B ikfkfed fo|ky; p; fur fd; js bu fo|ky; ka l s l EcfUkr 2500 mRrjnkrkvla ds }jkk
n"Vdksk eki u grq Lofufe' iz ukoythj erkoythj nRr l adyu i= ds }jkk ikr vka dMa ds
fo'y\$kk k grq Økflrd vuqkr %R% x² dk iz, kx fd; k x; k g\$ rnkj jkUr eq; fu"d"z bl
izlkj g\$ % ljdkjh ikfkfed fo|ky; ka dh vi\$kk xj&ljdkjh ikfkfed fo|ky; ka ea
voLFtki uk l fo|kk; } f'k{k d Nk= vuqkr] xqtoRrk; Ør ; kst uk; } [ky d m dh l fo|kk; }
ijh{kkQy} 'k\$kd okrtoj. k] Hkk"kk rFkk xf.krh; fodkl] l ok\$ch.k fodkl] Nk= mi fLFkr]
dk; Zfnol ka dh l f; k J\$B i k; h x; hA %xj&ljdkjh ikfkfed fo|ky; ka dh vi\$kk ljdkjh
ikfkfed fo|ky; ka ea f'k{k d ; k\$; rth] Nk= ukeddu %xjch j\$kk l s uhp\$ f'k{k.k dk; Z ds
vfrfjDrk voj\$kd] Nk=ka ds i fr Hk\$Hko jfgr okrtoj.k J\$B i k; s x; A i ktr 'k\$ ds fu"d"z
vflHk\$odka dks J\$B fo|ky; ka ds p; u grq] ikfkfed fo|ky; ka ds l pkyu] m\$ga ell; rk
in ku djus ea f'k{k vflkdkfj; ka dks l gk; rk in ku dj\$ s l kfk gh 'k\$ Nk=ka dks l gk; rk
in ku dj\$ s

i Lrkouk&

oržeku l e; ea dkuig e. My ea vusd izdkj ds fo |ky;] i kFkfed Lrj ij l pkyr gA
ijlurq mudh JSBrk] fo f'k"Vrk , oa egrRk bu i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh xqkoRrk ij vk/kkfjr gksh gA
fofHkuu izdkj ds fo |ky; ka ea dN fo |ky; fo'kSk i fl f) , oa [; kfr i ktr ns[ks x; s gA izsk ds l e;
vf/kdrj turk dk l pko dN fo f'k"V] i fl) i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vkj ns[ks x; k gA vkf[kj , d s
dks l s rRo gA tks l keku; & tuekul dks fo f'k"V izdkj ds i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vkj vkdf'kr djrs
gA

vr% l kožkksed f'k{kk ds fodkl ds l kFk&l kFk i kFkfed Lrj ij l jdkjh , oa xš&l jdkjh
i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh JSBrk ea l gk; d dkjdka dk rnyukRed v/; ; u vr; Ur vko' ; d gA

i R; ; ka dk i fjHkk"khdj.k

i kFkfed Lrj& ^og fo |ky; h Lrj ftl ea 6 l s 14 o"lz ds fo |kFkhZ v/; ; u djrs gA
i kFkfed Lrj dgykrk gA bl ds vlurxZ i kFkfed rFkk mPp i kFkfed fo |ky; vkrs gA**

l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; & ^os i kFkfed fo |ky; ftudh 0; oLFkk , oa [kpZ l jdkj ds v/khu
gkrs gš l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; dgykrs gA**

xš&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; & ^os i kFkfed fo |ky; ftudh l kjh 0; oLFkk , oa [kpZ fdl h
0; fDr ¼ i zU/kd½ ds v/khu gkrs gš xš&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; dgykrs gA**

JSBrk& ^fdl h 0; fDr] oLrj fopkj] ; k vkn'kz dk mRd"V Lrj] ml dh JSBrk dgykrh gA**

JSBrk ea l gk; d dkjd& ^os dkjd tks fdl h 0; fDRk] oLrj fopkj] ; k vkn'kz dks mRd"Brk
i nku djrs gš JSBrk ea l gk; d dkjd dgykrs gA**

v/; ; u dk egRo

'kks/kdrkz dk fopkj gSfd i R; d i kFkfed Lrj ds fo |ky; dks mRre , oa JSB Js kh ea gh gksuk
pkfg,] D; kkd i kFkfed f'k{kk] l Ei wkz f'k{kk dk vk/kkj vFkkZ~ tM+gksh gA tM+dks etcir djuk] ml s

fl fipr djuk ge l Hkh dk i Fke drD; gA bl h mnns ; l s 'kkkdrkz us ^i kFkfed Lrj ij l jdkjh , oa xj&l jdkjh fo |ky; ka dh JSBrk ea l gk; d dkjdka dk rgyukRed v/; ; u** fd; k gA bu dkjdka dk vuq j.k djus l s i kFkfed Lrj dsfo |ky; ka dh fo"kerk gh l eklr gks tk, xhA

v/; ; u dsmnns ;

i Lrj 'kkk l eL; k ds fuEu 12 iedk mnns ; fu/kkZjr fd; sx; sg%

- 1- 1/2-1/2 fo |ky; ka dh JSBrk ea l gk; d dkjdka dk l jdkjh , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka rFkk 'kgjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xkeh.k i kFkfed fo |ky; ka l s rgyuk djuka
- 2 1/4[k-1/2 fo |ky; ka dh JSBrk ea l gk; d dkjdka dks i kB; Øe ea vi ukdj i kjfEHkd f'k{kk dks JSB cukuka

ifjdYi uk; &

i Lrj v/; ; u , d vkn'kkRed l oZk.k gA bl dh ed; ifjdYi uk, afuEufyf[kr g&

- 1- l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh ekudka ds vuq i voLFkki uk l fpo/kkvka ea dkbZ vUrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 2- l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea xjhch jSkk l s uhps jgus okys cPka ds ukekadu ea dkbZ vUrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 3- l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea f'k{k d&Nk= vuq kr ea dkbZ vUrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 4- l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea f'k{k dka }kj k f'k{k.k dk; Z ds vfrfjDr vU; dk; Z djus ea dkbZ vUrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 5- l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ds f'k{k dka dh ; kk; rk ea dkbZ vUrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA

- 6- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea Nk=ka grq mi yC/k xqkoRrk ; qR ; kstukvka ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 7- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea Nk=ka dks [ksydm dh l fo/kkvka ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 8- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka rFkk xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ds i jh{kQy ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 9- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka rFkk xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ds 'kS{k d okrkoj .k ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 10- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka rFkk xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea Hk"kk rFkk xf.krh; fodkl ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 11- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka rFkk xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ds Nk=ka ds l okh.k fodkl ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 12- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka rFkk xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea Nk=ka ds i fr Hks&Hko jfgr okrkoj .k ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 13- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea Nk=ka dh mi fLFkr ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 14- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea dk; Z fnol ka dh l q; k ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA
- 15- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka , oa xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea f'k(k.k dk; Z ds vojkskdka ea dkbZ vlrj ugha i k; k tkrk gA

ifj l heu

- 1- i Lr 'kksk dk; Z ea dpy i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dks l fefyr fd; k x; k gA
- 2- i Lr 'kksk l eL; k ds vlrxr dpy dkuij e.My dh i kj fEkd f'k{k ds fodkl ij n"Vikr fd; k x; k gA

- 3- bl v/; ; u ea l UnHkZ ds : i ea vuqNsn 45 , oa 46 ds vuq kj] xqkoRrk ds dkjdka ds fy, e.My ds l Hkh ftyka ea l s 20&20 ¼120 th0, l 0½ \$ 120 ¼, u0th0l h0½ = 240 i kjfEHkd fo |ky; ka dh J\$Brk dks ekik tk; sk rFkk J\$Brk ea l gk; d dkjdka dk v/; ; u fd; k tk; skA
- 4- iLr r v/; ; u ea p; fur N% ftyka ds i kFkfed f'k{k ds f0; kUo; u ea l gk; d i zkkukpk;] f'k{k(d] izU/kd] l epk;] ekrk&fi rk] l j {kdka xteh.k f'k{k l fefr; ka ds l nL; ka dh Hkxhnhkj h dks Kkr fd; k x; k gS bl h Hkxhnhkj ds vk/kkj ij Kkr fd; s x; A felnyka l s J\$Brk ea l gk; d dkjdka dks [kkst k x; k gA

'kks'k fof/k

bl v/; ; u ea eyr% l oZk.k fof/k dk iz xs fd; k x; k gA pfd iLr r 'kks'k l eL; k dk v/; ; u vkn'kZnyd l oZk.k }kjk fd; k tk; skA bl fy, 'kks'kdrkZ }kjk viuh l jyrk ds fy, iz ukoyh] erkoyh , oanRr l dyu i i = dk fuekZk fd; k x; k gA

tu l ; k , oa i frn'kZ

iLr r 'kks'k v/; ; u ea dkuij e.My ds vLrxZ N% ftyka dkuij uxj] dkuij ngkr] vk\$S k] bVkok] Q: [kkkn] dluks ds l Ei wkZ i kFkfed fo |ky; vkrs gS ftudh l ; k 14943 gS tks dkuij e.My ds 50 Cykdka l s l Ec) gS buea 14219 l j djh i kFkfed fo |ky; , oa 724 xj l j djh i kFkfed fo |ky; vkrs gA

'kks'k ea iz 0r pj

Lora= pj& i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh J\$Brk ea l gk; d dkjdA
vkfJr pj& i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh J\$BrkA

l k[; dh; fof/k; k& vkdMka ds fo'y'sk.k gsrq e/; eku rFkk ekud fopyu dk iz xs fd; k x; kA nks fofHku l eyka ds e/; l kFkd vLrj Kkr djus gsrq 0kflrd vuq kr ¼.R.½ dk iz xs fd; k x; k gA nks l eyka ds fofHku dkjdka ds e/; l kFkd vLrj Kkr djus gsrq x² ; k iz xs fd; k x; k gA

rkfydk &1

I jdkjh rFkk xj&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo | ky; ka dh J\$Brk ea l gk; d dkj dka
dh rgyuk

J\$Brk ea l gk; d dkj d	N	Men	SD.	Men	Df	C.R.
ekudka ds vk/kkj ij voLFkki uk l fo/kk, i	500	4.566	1.169	1-70	998	20-737
	500	6.266	1.412			**
ukekdu	500	1.996	0.801	1.026	998	23.680
	500	0.970	0.545			**
f' k{k d Nk= vuq kr	500	0.236	0.282	0.482	998	21.876
	500	0.718	0.404			**
f' k{k dka }kjk f' k{k.k dk; l dh vfrfjDr vu; dk; l	500	5.230	1.341	4.422	998	44.336
	500	9.652	1.782			**
f' k{k dka dh ; kx; rk	500	0.700	0.424	0.392	998	16.520
	500	0.308	0.319			**
Nk=ka gsrq mi yC/k	500	3.216	1.001			29.466

xqkoRrk; Ør ; kst uk, j	500	5.428	1.340	2.212	998	**
Nk=ka dks mi yC/k	500	1.854	0.773	2.336	998	36.963
[ky&dñ dh l qo/kk; a	500	4.190	1.183			**
ijh{kQy	500	0.542	0.424	0.348	998	11.438
	500	0.890	0.532			**
'k{k d okrkoj .k	500	0.470	0.376	1.194	998	32.444
	500	1.664	0.732			**
Hkk'kk rFkk xf.krh; fodk' k	500	0.904	0.547	0.604	998	15.136
	500	1.508	0.705			**
Nk=ka ds l okxh.k fodkl	500	2.980	0.988	1.848	998	25.757
	500	4.828	1.264			**
Nk=ka ds i fr HknHkko jfgr okrkoj .k	500	3.722	1.095	0.506	998	7.564
	500	3.216	1.019			**
Nk=ka dh mi fLFkr	120	81.70	5.167	12.05	238	17.277
	120	93.75	5.628			**

dk; Z fno l ka dh I 0	120	227.025	6.660	.916	238	8.884
	120	236.941	8.709			**

**** - 05 , oa-01 I kFkZrk Lrj ij I kFkZd gA**

rkydk & 2

I jdkjh rFk xj & I jdkjh i kFkfed fo | ky; ka ea i k; s tkus okys f'k{k.k dk; Z

ds vojks/kdka dh rgyuka

I eng		tux.kuk	lkou fuekZk	fuokpu dk; Z	feM&Ms ehy	fyfi dh; dk; Z	; kx	χ^2
I jdkjh i kfofo0 ¼120½	F0	109	5-2	114	99	109	483	63.04
	Fe	104.46	49.83	109.25	94.88	124.58		
xj I jdkjh i kfofo0 ¼120½	F0	'kkl;	'kkl;	'kkl;	'kkl;	21		**
	Fe	4-54	2-17	4-75	4-12	5-42		
; kx		109	52	114	99	130	504	

**** - 05 , oa-01 I kFkZrk Lrj ij I kFkZd gA**

fu"d"k& i klr ifj.kkeka ds vk/kkj ij fuEufyf[kr fu"d"kz fudkys tk l drs g&

- 1- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea ik; h tkus okyh voLFkki uk l qo/kk, a JSB gA
- 2- x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea xjhch j\$kk l s uhps jgus okys cPpka dk ukeadu Lrj JSB gA
- 3- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea ik; k tkus okyk f'k{k d&Nk= vuq kr JSB g\$ vFkkz~ifr f'k{k d Nk=ka dh l q; k de jgrh gA
- 4- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea f'k{k dka }kj k f'k{k.k dk; Z ds vfrfjDr vu; dk; Z djus dh l q; k vf/kd gA
- 5- x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea f'k{k dka dh ; kx; rk JSB gA
- 6- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea Nk=ka g\$ q vf/kd l q; k ea xqkorrk; q; r ; kst uk, a mi yC/k gA
- 7- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea ik; h tkus okyh [ky&dm dh l qo/kk, a JSB gA
- 8- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dk i jh{kQy JSB gA
- 9- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea ik; k tkus okyk 'k\$kd okrkoj.k JSB gA
- 10- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea ik; k tkus okyk Hkk"kk rFkk xf.krh; fodkl JSB gA
- 11- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea Nk=ka dk l okach.k fodkl JSB gA
- 12- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk x\$&I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea ik; k tkus okyk Nk=ka ds ifr HksrHkko jfgr okrkoj.k JSB gA

- 13- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk xj & I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea i k; h tkus okyh Nk=ka dh mi fLFkfr vf/kd JSB gA
- 14- I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk xj & I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea dk; Z fnol ka dh I d; k vf/kd JSB gA
- 15- xj & I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh vi \$kk I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea f'k{k.k dk; Z ds vojkskd vf/kd I d; k ea i k; s tkrsgA

'kFkd egRo

1- i nkZuoku gsrq vuq z kx

JSBrk ea l gk; d dkj dka ds vk/kkj ij l eLr izdkj ds i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh JSBrk Lrj dk i nkZuoku yxk; k tk l drk gA

- ❖ fdl h i kFkfed fo |ky; dh 'kFkd fu"i fRr dk i nkZuoku yxk; k tk l drk gA
- ❖ 'kFkd fu"i fRRK ds vk/kkj ij fo |ky; ds 'kFkd okrkj.k dk i nkZuoku yxk; k tk l drk gA
- ❖ xjhch j\$kk l suhps jgus okys fo |kFkz; ka dh 'kFkd fu"i fRr ds dkj.k ka dk i nkZuoku yxk; k tk l drk gA

2- 'kFkd ; kst ukvka ds dk; k l o; u gsrq vuq z kx

- ❖ fo |ky; ka dh izl/ku ; kst ukvka ea v/; ; u ds i fj.kkka dk fØ; k l o; u fd; k tk l drk g\$ bl l s fo |ky; ka ds xqkoRrk Lrj ea l dkkj gkskA
- ❖ v/; ; u ds i fj.kkka dk I jdkjh f'k{k.k ; kst ukvka ea dk; k l o; u djds I jdkjh f'k{k.k I l Fk vka dh xqkoRrk Lrj ea l dkkj fd; k tk l drk gA

3- fdl h f'k{k.k I l Fk dh vl Qyrk ds dkj.k ka dk i rk yxkus gsrq vuq z kx

fdl h f'k{k.k I l Fk ml u; u gsrq ml ea JSB fo |ky; h dkj dka dh mi fLFkfr vko'; d g\$ vr% fdl h f'k{k.k I l Fk dh vl Qyrk bl ckr dh |ksd g\$fd ml I l Fk ea mi jkDr JSB dkj dka ea l s vf/kdrj vuq LFkfr gA

4- i kFkfed f'k{k k ea vuq z kx

- ❖ I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ea f'k{k k dks f'k{k.k dk; Z ds vfrfjDr t\$ & tux.kuk] Hkou fuekZk] fuokpu dk; Z feM&Ms eh] fyfi dh; dk; Z t\$ s vuq dk; Z djus iMf s gs ftl l s mudk f'k{k.k dk; Z i kFkfor gkrk gA vr% bu dk; ka dk fuokj.k djds I jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ds f'k{k.k Lrj ea l qkkj fd; k tk l drk gA
- ❖ I gk; d l kexh ds iz kx }kjk f'k{k.k dk; Z dks l jy , oackkxE; cuk; k tk l drk gA

5- vU; vuq z kx

- ❖ f'k{k.k l i kFk ea f'k{k k , oavfHkHkod l ak dh 0; oLFk djds l i kFk dh dfe; ka dh tkudkj dh tk l drh gA
- ❖ fo |ky; ds fu; fer i ; b{k.k }kjk fo |ky; ka dh JSBrk cuk; sj [kh tk l drh gA

Hkkoh v/; ; u gsrq l qko

- ❖ i Lrj 'kk{k dk; Z dkuij e.My ds l nHkZ ea fd; k x; k g\$ bl s insk] nsk , oavUrkZVh; Lrj ij fd; k tk l drk gA
- ❖ i Lrj 'kk{k dk; Z dby i kFkfed fo |ky; Lrj ij fd; k x; k] bl s ek/; fed , oamPp Lrj ij Hkh fd; k tk l drk gA
- ❖ i Lrj 'kk{k dk; Z ea l jdkjh rFk x\$&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dk ^kgjh l jdkjh rFk 'kgjh x\$ l jdkjh** , oaxkeh.k l jdkjh rFk xkeh.k x\$&l jdkjh** i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ds l nHkZ ea v/; ; u fd; k x; k g\$ bl s ^kgjh l jdkjh i kFkfed rFk xkeh.k x\$&l jdkjh , oaxkeh.k l jdkjh rFk 'kgjh x\$&l jdkjh i kFkfed fo |ky; ka ds l nHkZ ea v/; ; u fd; k tk l drk gA
- ❖ i Lrj 'kk{k dk; Z ek=kRed izdkj dk g\$ bl dk xqkkRed 'kk{k fd; k tk l drk gA
- ❖ i Lrj v/; ; u i kFkfed fo |ky; ka dh JSBrk ea dN l hfer i Lrj v/; ; u ea dkjdka dks vk/kk cuk; k x; k g\$ bl ea JSBrk ea l gk; d vU; dkjdka dks Hkh fy; k tk l drk gA

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- 18 H k k j r d k l f i o / k k u - ¼ 1981½ f g l n h v u p k n l f i o / k k u d s 44 o a l d k k s / k u l f g r j l b v y y k , t b l h A
- 19 e y s k j d o l h o - ¼ 1988½ f ' k { k k i z k k l u , o a i ; b s k . A H k k s k y % e l ; i n s k f g l n h x d f k v d k n e h A
- 20 e k f k j] M k o , l o , l o - ¼ 1994½ f o / k y ; l a B u , o a l o k l f ; f ' k { k k] e j B % j l r k s x h i f c y d s k u A
- 21 f e j k] M k o M h o l h o - ¼ 2004½ f ' k { k k ' k k l = H k k x & , d r f k k n k j d k u i g % v u d d k k u i d k ' k u A
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- 24 J h o k l r o j f ' k o k u n ¼ M o k s d v ½ ¼ 2002½ m o i d c f l d f ' k { k k l f g r k , o a v f / k f u ; e j b y k g k c k n % f g l n h i f c y f ' k a k g k m l A